

Baker_et_al_Code_Dryad_Figures

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Required Data

To run this script, please add the following files to your working directory:

Baker_2022_All_Ambient_Loggers_CSV.csv

Baker_2022_Experimental_Warming_Loggers_CSV.csv

Baker_2022_Behavior_CSV.csv

Baker_2022_Physiology_CSV.csv

Baker_2022_Survival_CSV.csv

Baker_2022_Community_Data_CSV.csv

Packages to Load

```
##  
## Attaching package: 'dplyr'  
  
## The following objects are masked from 'package:stats':  
##  
##   filter, lag  
  
## The following objects are masked from 'package:base':  
##  
##   intersect, setdiff, setequal, union  
  
## Linking to GEOS 3.10.2, GDAL 3.4.2, PROJ 8.2.1; sf_use_s2() is TRUE  
  
##  
## Attaching package: 'cowplot'
```

```
## The following object is masked from 'package:gpubr':  
##  
##   get_legend
```

Checking Versions

```
## [1] "dplyr"  
## [1] '1.1.2'  
## [1] "ggplot2"  
## [1] '3.4.2'  
## [1] "gpubr"  
## [1] '0.6.0'  
## [1] "sciplot"  
## [1] '1.2.0'  
## [1] "maps"  
## [1] '3.4.1'  
## [1] "sf"  
## [1] '1.0.12'  
## [1] "rnaturalearth"  
## [1] '0.3.2'  
## [1] "ggspatial"  
## [1] '1.1.8'  
## [1] "cowplot"  
## [1] '1.1.3'  
## [1] "R"  
## [1] "R version 4.2.2 (2022-10-31)"
```

Figure 1: Geographic distribution of sites and their thermal regimes

```
## [1] "This map purely for visualization, so spherical geometries are turned off"  
## Spherical geometry (s2) switched off  
## although coordinates are longitude/latitude, st_intersection assumes that they  
## are planar  
## although coordinates are longitude/latitude, st_intersection assumes that they  
## are planar  
## although coordinates are longitude/latitude, st_intersection assumes that they  
## are planar
```


Figure 2: Influence of experimental warming on thermal regimes

Figure 4: Effects of experimental warming on grasshopper behavior and physiology across Site types and predation risk

Figure 5: Effects of grasshopper plasticity on *Solidago* biomass across Site types and predation risk

Figure S1: Effects of experimental warming on grasshopper survival across Site types and predation risk

Figure S2: Effects of grasshopper plasticity on grass biomass across Site types and predation risk

